

Effect of Variation of Particle Size and Agitation on the Flocculation of Coals by Polymeric Flocculants

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One of the proven methods for the recovery of coal fines from -and simultaneous recovery of, washery waste waters and effluent is the process of flocculation, for which the polymeric flocculants have been found to be very suitable¹⁻³. Extensive investigations have been carried out on different aspects of flocculation of coal fines by polymeric flocculants establishing the effectiveness of the process of flocculation in the recovery of coal fines and in the minimisation of water pollution to a great extent⁴⁻⁶.

Since the process of flocculation is dependent to a great extent upon several parameters, it was expedient to study the effect of these parameters individually in some detail.

The present paper reports the results of the effect of variation of particle size and of agitation on the flocculation behaviour of some bituminous coals of Jharia coalfield by a few polymeric flocculants viz. hydrolysed polyacrylamide and califloc.

Results and Discussion

Proximate and ultimate analysis data of different coal samples are given in Table 1.

The results of settling rates of different particle size of Busseryya, Digwadih and Ramkanali coals flocculated with HPAM and califloc are presented in Table 2. The results on the effect of agitation on flocculation of these coals flocculated with HPAM only are included in Table 3.

Earlier workers reported^{3,5} that the effective particle size for maximum settling of coal particles

is 30–52 mesh, which agrees well with the present results. Although the percentage of fine particles below 53 μ was more (about 30–40%) in our samples in comparison with those reported by Banerjee *et al.*³ (10–25%), the settling rates are comparatively higher, especially in case of flocculation with HPAM, which is probably due to its better efficiency.

TABLE 1—PROXIMATE AND ULTIMATE ANALYSIS AND CALORIFIC VALUES OF BUSSERIYA, DIGWADIH AND RAMKANALI COALS

Sl no		Busseryya	Digwadih	Ramkanali
1	Proximate analysis			
	Moisture (%)	1 20	1 0	1 10
	Ash (%)	16 00	21 9	33 05
	V M (%)	24 20	24 8	19 80
	F C (%)	59 60	52 3	47 05
2	Ultimate analysis (dmnf, basis)			
	C (%)	90 00	89 8	91 3
	H (%)	4 7	5 0	4 9
	N (%)	1 9	2 0	2 0
	S (%)	0 7	0 6	0 7
	O % (by diff)	2 7	2 6	1 1
3	Calorific value (kcal kg ⁻¹)	8 700	8 720	8 785
4	Caking Index	26	17	16

That the settling rate diminishes with decrease in particle size is explicable on the basis of charge neutralisation phenomenon. In the case of finer coal particles, high increasing surface area increases the charge. But due to the fixed dosage and concentration of the polymer (flocculant), the charge on it always remains the same. In the course of flocculation, when the charge on the polymer flocculant is fully neutralised or counterbalanced, it is probably the

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF PARTICLE SIZE ON THE FLOCCULATION OF BUSSERIYA, DIGWADIH AND RAMKANALI COALS FLOCCULATED WITH HPAM AND CALIFLOC*

Coal	Settling rate (cm min ⁻¹) of coal for particle size (μ)						
	50	100	150	200	300	400	500
Busseriya	21.1	25.5	28.0	29.7	30.0	30.4	30.4
	(17.9)	20.6	21.6	22.2	22.2	22.5	22.1)
Digwadih	20.0	23.1	24.5	25.4	26.0	26.1	26.1
	(14.0)	16.5	18.0	18.2	18.2	18.5	18.3)
Ramkanali	16.8	20.0	21.0	21.9	22.2	22.4	22.5
	(11.0)	14.0	14.6	15.0	15.4	15.3	15.0)

* Califloc data in parenthesis.

stage of maximum settling observed at 400 μ. However, as the particle size further decreases, the charge on them accordingly increases and becomes somewhat in excess in comparison to that on the polymer, with the net result that charge on the coal particles remains uncounterbalanced. Due to this reason the excess charge takes part in hindering the bridging already taken place, resulting eventually in decrease of settling rate. Furthermore, because finer particles being lighter in weight and buoyancy of the liquid being comparatively higher, these finer particles, in accordance with Stoke's law, remain suspended in the solution for a long time, and due to which the settling is slower as evidenced by lower settling rates for extremely fine particles below 100 μ.

Another possible explanation for the observed lower settling rates in case of finer particles (below 400 μ) could be the ion-bonding between the fixed charge of the polyion of the flocculant and the counter-ions of the coal particles as advocated by earlier workers⁷. The ion-bonding between the flocculant and coal particle takes place due to the electrostatic forces. In the initial stages, the magnitude of ion-bonding being greater the settling rates are higher. However, with decreasing particle size, the excess charge on them due to higher surface area, predominates ion-bonding and in turn retards the bridge formation, and thus the settling rate decreases. It seems quite probable that below the particle size of 400 μ such a situation prevails and thus lower settling rates are observed.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF AGITATION ON FLOCCULATION OF BUSSERIYA, DIGWADIH AND RAMKANALI COALS WITH HPAM

Mode of agitation	Settling rate (cm min ⁻¹)		
	Busseriya	Digwadih	Ramkanali
(A) End-to-end inversions :			
No. of inversion			
10	28.0	23.5	18.1
20	27.9	23.2	18.2
30	27.6	23.0	17.8
40	27.4	22.8	17.4
50	26.6	22.5	17.0
60	26.0	21.5	15.0
70	24.1	20.5	12.9
80	23.0	18.9	10.9
90	20.0	17.0	—
100	18.0	—	—
(B) Vigorous agitation :			
Time of agitations			
10	31.3	26.0	22.1
20	30.5	25.5	21.9
30	29.5	25.0	19.0
40	28.1	23.6	17.9
50	27.0	21.5	15.0
60	23.9	20.0	12.0
70	20.0	16.6	—
80	16.9	—	—

The observation that in case of mild agitation imparted to the system through end-to-end inversions does not practically affect the settling rate initially upto 30–40 inversions, is explicable on the basis that time taken for 30–40 inversions is too short to bring the adsorbed flocculant molecule to a saturation level and as such is ineffective to break the already formed flocs. As the number of inversions is increased beyond 40, the saturation level of the adsorbed flocculant is reached rather quickly with the setting in of 'breakdown' of flocs. In this process, new surface charges are generated for which the neutralisation of additional quantity of flocculant is needed. However, since the polymer concentration and dosage are fixed, the extra flocculant needed for neutralisation of the newly generated charges is not available, and hence the charges remain unneutralised as a result of which bridging is hindered. The net result is lowering of settling rates, which is really observed for higher number of inversions.

Furthermore, it was observed (Table 2) that vigorous agitation causes breaking down of the flocs more quickly. Also the rate of settling is affected by the duration of shaking. As the duration of agitation is increased, the settling rate is lowered. This observation is in close agreement with the earlier results on flocculation of coal slurries from different washeries using various flocculants¹. It was also reported⁸ that vigorous agitation breaks down the already formed flocs quickly and with the increase of the breaking down of flocs, the settling rate decreases.

Alinec and Robertson⁹ reported that the energy supplied by high speed stirring (similar to the vibratory motion imparted by mechanical shaking in the present work) is sufficient to cause 'breaking down' of the polymer bridges between the particles. These investigators stressed that very vigorous agitation is detrimental to floc formation. The greater lowering of settling rate due to vigorous agitation is explicable on the basis of the mechanism suggested by Smoluchowski¹⁰. The study reveals that vigorous agitation is harmful for flocculation and in fact hinders the floc-formation, and that the process of flocculation is governed by both charge neutralisation and bridging phenomenon.

Experimental

The methods of preparation of flocculant solution and coal slurry preparation are described elsewhere⁵. The flocculation tests were carried out by determining the settling rates for the coals, for which 6% slurries of each of the coal samples of particle size 50, 100, 150, 200, 300, 400, 500 μ separately employed for individual flocculation test with HPAM and califloc flocculants, their dosage being 3 ml (of 0.1% polymer solution). The settling rate experiments were performed in a neutral slurry media (pH = 7.0) and at room temperature ($\approx 25^\circ$). The effect of agitation on flocculation was studied by determining the settling rate after mild and vigorous agitation of the system in two ways : (i) the manual,

fixed number of end-to-end inversions of the cylinders employed for flocculation tests and (ii) mechanical shaking, by imparting the system a vibratory motion on an electrical shaker for different time periods. Here the particle size of the coals was kept constant (36 mesh of 400 μ).

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